

Laboratory protocol handbook for proteomic analysis of airway mucins in sputum from asthmatic patients

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1. Objective

Mucins are a heterogeneous family of high-molecular-weight, gel-forming glycoproteins that assemble into polymeric structures reaching 5–50 MDa¹. In the airways, mucins MUC5AC and MUC5B are the main structural components of mucus and are central to the pathology of muco-obstructive diseases, such as asthma^{2,3}. Their excessive production leads to mucus plugging, airway obstruction, and an increased likelihood of disease exacerbations⁴.

Despite their clinical relevance, the biochemical analysis of mucins presents significant challenges due to their large size, O-glycosylation, and the high viscosity of sputum matrices⁵. The aim of this protocol was to establish a simplified, reproducible, and standardized workflow for the efficient extraction, processing, and proteomic profiling of mucins from sputum samples. This approach was designed to facilitate reliable comparison of mucin profiles across asthmatic phenotypes and to support the development of mucin-based biomarkers for muco-obstructive diseases.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Population of study and Bioethics

This research was conducted at the Laboratory of Biological Chemistry of the School of Medicine at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), in collaboration with the First Laboratory of Pharmacology of the School of Medicine at AUTH. The study included four patients with asthma who were hospitalized in the Pulmonary Department of “Hippokration” General Hospital of Thessaloniki, as well as one healthy individual. The diagnosis of asthma was established according to the criteria of the Global Initiative for Asthma⁶. None of the participants suffered from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), cystic or pulmonary fibrosis, bronchiectasis, or any other significant comorbidity, such as malignancy, cardiac, renal, hepatic disease, or connective tissue disease. Patients with nasal polyps or symptoms of chronic sinusitis were also excluded, as these conditions are known to be associated with mucus hypersecretion.

The research protocol used in the present study was approved by the Bioethics and Ethics Committee of the School of Medicine at AUTH. Additionally, permission was obtained from “Hippokration” General Hospital of Thessaloniki for the retrieval of data from the collaborating clinics, where the study participants were hospitalized. Finally, all participants provided written informed consent to participate in the study.

2.2 Sputum samples collection

A. Reagents

- Hypertonic NaCl solution (4.5% w/v)

- Salbutamol (200 mg/dose)

B. Equipment & Materials

- Ultrasonic nebulizer (De Vilbiss)
- Sterile specimen containers, screw cap (for sputum collection) (50 mL)
- Spirometer

C. Procedure

The induced sputum collection procedure was carried out at the asthma outpatient clinic of the Pulmonary Department of “Hippokration” General Hospital of Thessaloniki. These samples provide a direct representation of airway secretions, offering valuable information about inflammatory processes in asthma. Sputum induction was performed according to published protocols^{7,8}. It is a simple, relatively non-invasive, and short-duration examination. Briefly, the procedure involves inhalation of a hypertonic NaCl solution for a total of 15 minutes using an ultrasonic nebulizer, while lung function testing is performed beforehand, and a preventive inhaled bronchodilator is administered. The exact protocol for sputum induction is described below:

Minimizing salivary contamination

- Instruct the participant to thoroughly rinse their mouth with water and expectorate.

Nebulizer output settings

- Adjust the De Vilbiss nebulizer to a flow rate of 1 mL/min and load the 4.5% w/v hypertonic NaCl solution.

Premedication and prediction of excessive bronchospasm

- Perform spirometry to measure forced expiratory volume in the first second (FEV₁) and peak expiratory flow (PEF).
- Administer 200 mg inhaled salbutamol and repeat the FEV₁ and PEF measurements after 10 minutes.

Nebulization and sputum collection

- Instruct the participant to inhale the nebulized solution for 5 minutes, then cough and expectorate.

Monitoring pulmonary function- safety measurements

- After each 5-minute period, repeat spirometry, and stop the procedure if a decrease in FEV₁ or PEF, greater than 20%, occurs. The total duration of the procedure should not exceed 15 minutes and may be stopped at any time at the participant's request.

The procedure was safely performed in three patients and one healthy volunteer. In one patient with poor pulmonary function (FEV1 < 35%), induction was not performed. Instead, sputum was collected through spontaneous expectoration to ensure safety. Sputum samples were considered adequate if the participant could expectorate a volume of ≥ 2 mL. The samples were frozen and stored at -20°C for 30–240 minutes. Subsequently, they were aliquoted in Eppendorf tubes to avoid repeated freeze-thaw cycles and to preserve mucin polymer integrity. Finally, samples were transferred to -80°C for long-term storage.

2.3 Solubilization of sputum samples

A. Reagents

- Urea (Applichem; A1049)
- Guanidine (Sigma-Aldrich; G4630)
- RIPA lysis buffer, 10x (Merck Millipore; 20-188)
- Tris base (Applichem; A1086)
- Hydrochloric acid (HCl) (Merck; 1,00317)
- Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS) (Sigma Aldrich; L5750)
- Phenylmethylsulfonyl Fluoride (PMSF) (Sigma Aldrich; 78830)
- Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail I (Sigma Aldrich; 524624)
- Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail II (Sigma Aldrich; 524625)
- Protease Inhibitor Cocktail Set III, EDTA-Free (Merck; 539134)
- Dithiothreitol (DTT) (Applichem; A1101)
- ddH₂O

B. Equipment & Materials

- Ultrasonic cleaner (Fischer Scientific; FS 28H)
- Vortex mixer (FastGene Vortexer Mini; NIPPON Genetics)
- Refrigerated Microcentrifuge (KUBOTA;3520)
- Mechanical micropipettes (100-1,000 μL , 20-200 μL , 0.5-10 μL)
- Pipette Tips (10 μL , 200 μL , 1,000 μL)
- Eppendorf tubes (2 mL, 1.5 mL)

C. Procedure

To determine the optimal extraction method, four different lysis buffers were evaluated for the solubilization of sputum samples. The **first lysis buffer** consisted of Urea/Guanidine (**U/Gn**; 8 M Urea, 3 M Guanidine). The **second lysis buffer** was a 10x RIPA buffer (Merck), which was diluted to a 2x working solution and added to two samples to achieve a final concentration of 1x. The **third lysis buffer** was prepared using 100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.6 and 4% SDS (Tris/SDS). The **fourth lysis buffer** consisted

of a 1:1 mixture of RIPA buffer and the Tris/SDS solution (RIPA: Tris/SDS, 1:1). The exact protocol used for the solubilization of sputum samples is the following:

Preparation of lysis buffers

- Prepare the lysis buffers.
- Just prior to usage, add the following inhibitors per mL of buffer: Add PMSF to the RIPA lysis buffer, at a final concentration of 1mM. In addition, add 10 µL of phosphatase inhibitors (Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail I, Sigma Aldrich and Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail II, Sigma Aldrich) and 10 µL of protease inhibitors (Protease Inhibitor Cocktail Set III, EDTA-Free, Merck) to the same lysis buffer. Finally, add DTT to the RIPA buffer and the three other lysis solutions at a final concentration of 2 mM.

Sample preparation (incubation, homogenization, clarification)

- Thaw samples on ice.
- Add ~250 µL from the original sputum samples to each lysis buffer at a 1:1 ratio.
- For U/Gn samples: Incubate for 5 days with gentle agitation at 4°C. For all other samples, proceed to the next step. Apply this step to the U/Gn samples as well after their incubation.
- Mix by pipetting all samples (using a 1,000 µL tip).
- Place samples in an ultrasonic bath for 10 minutes (cycles: 30 sec ON, 30 sec OFF).
- Incubate samples with gentle agitation for 20 minutes at 4°C.
- Centrifugate samples at 10,000 × g, 4°C, for 15 minutes.

Storage

- Transfer supernatants obtained after centrifugation to new Eppendorf tubes and discard pellets.
- Store samples at -80°C, until further processing.

2.4 Determination of protein concentration

A. Reagents

- Bradford Dye Reagent Concentrate (Bio-Rad; 5000006)
- Albumin (BSA) (Appllichem; A1391,0100)
- ddH₂O

B. Equipment & Materials

- Spectrophotometer (Eppendorf Bio Photometer; 6131)
- Cuvettes (1,5 mL)
- Eppendorf tubes (1.5 mL)
- Mechanical micropipettes (20-200 µL, 100-1,000 µL)

- Pipette Tips (200 μ L, 1,000 μ L)

C. Procedure

Protein concentration of the samples was determined using the Bradford assay, which was performed during the FASP protocol, before addition of trypsin (FASP protocol is described in Section 2.7), to prevent false-positive interference issues. Bradford analysis is based on the use of Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 (Coomassie G-250), which forms a blue complex in the presence of proteins. The Bradford reagent is an acidic red solution of Coomassie G-250, consisting of 0.01% (w/v) Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250, 4.7% (w/v) ethanol, and 8.5% (w/v) phosphoric acid, in its cationic, double protonated form. In the absence of protein, the Bradford reagent has a maximum absorbance (A_{\max}) at 470 nm, producing a red color. In the presence of protein, the transition to the anionic form of the dye shifts the A_{\max} to 595 nm, turning the color to blue. Since the amount of the blue anionic form is proportional to the amount of protein in the sample, the protein concentration can be measured directly by reading the absorbance at 595 nm⁹. The exact protocol used is described below:

Preparation of standards

- Prepare a range of BSA standards as shown in Table 1, to generate the calibration curve (Figure 1).

Assay Setup

- Add 1 mL of 1x Bradford reagent to the cuvettes.
- Add 20 μ L of known and unknown protein samples to the cuvettes and mix them with the Bradford reagent by pipetting.
- Incubate for 5 minutes at room temperature.

Measurements - Calculations

- Zero the spectrophotometer with the blank sample (0 mg/mL).
- Place the cuvettes with the known and unknown protein samples in the spectrophotometer to measure absorbance at 595 nm.
- Calculate protein concentration in the unknown samples, using the calibration curve generated from the standard solutions (Figure 1).

Table 1: Dilutions of the standard albumin solution

Protein Concentration (mg/mL)	Volume of 1mg/mL BSA standard (µL)	Volume of ddH ₂ O (µL)
0.00	0.00	100.00
0.05	5.00	95.00
0.10	10.00	90.00
0.20	20.00	80.00
0.40	40.00	60.00
0.60	60.00	40.00
0.80	80.00	20.00
1.00	100.00	0.00

Figure 1: Calibration curve for the Bradford assay, based on the absorbance values of the standard albumin solutions.

2.5 Denaturing separation of proteins (SDS-PAGE electrophoresis)

A. Reagents

Gel Casting

- 30% w/v T Acrylamide/Bis acrylamide solution (BioRad; 1610154)
- Tris base (Applichem; A1086,1000)
- Hydrochloric acid (HCl) (Merck; 1,00317,1000)
- Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate (SDS) (Sigma Aldrich; L5750)
- Ammonium persulfate (APS) (Panreac Applichem; A2941)

- TEMED (Applichem; A1148,0100)
- ddH₂O

Running & Loading

- Running Buffer 10x (Composition described in Table 4)
- Sample buffer 5x (with DTT) (Composition described in Table 3)
- BlueStar Prestained Protein Marker (NIPPON Genetics; MWPO4)

Staining

- Fixation solution (Composition described in Table 5)
- Coomassie Blue G-250 solution (Composition described in Table 6)

B. Equipment & Materials

- Refrigerated Microcentrifuge (KUBOTA; 3520)
- Imaging System (ChemiDoc MP; BioRad; 12003154)
- Heating Block (Kleinfeld; BT100)
- Casting frame (Mini PROTEAN Casting frame; BioRad; 1653304)
- Power Supply (PowerPac Basic Power Supply; BioRad; 1645050)
- Tetra Cell (Mini-PROTEAN Tetra Cell; BioRad; 1658001)
- Casting Module (Mini- PROTEAN Tetra Cell Casting Module; 1658015)
- Glass Plates (Mini-PROTEAN Glass Plates with 1.0 mm spacers; BioRad; 1653311)
- Short plates (Mini-PROTEAN Short plates; BioRad; 1653308)
- Comb (Mini-PROTEAN Comb, 10-well, 1.0 mm; BioRad; 1653359)
- Mechanical micropipettes (100-1,000 μ L, 20-200 μ L, 0.5-10 μ L)
- Falcons (15 mL, 50 mL)
- Eppendorf tips (10 μ L, 200 μ L, 1,000 μ L)
- Spatula (Gel releaser; BioRad; 1653320)
- Syringe (1cc Luer Slip Syringes and Conventional Needles; Terumo; 22290018)

C. Procedure

Electrophoresis is a method used to separate macromolecules in an electric field. This technique is used for separating molecules based on their size. Sodium dodecyl sulfate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) enables the estimation of the relative molecular mass of the separated macromolecules, their relative abundance in a sample, their distribution among different fractions, and the purity of protein samples. This method is based on the use of polyacrylamide gel, which forms a porous matrix that slows down the movement of larger molecules more than that of smaller ones. SDS, an anionic detergent, disrupts hydrophobic interactions within proteins and denatures their secondary and tertiary structures that are not linked by disulfide bonds (non-covalent bonds). SDS unfolds proteins into their primary

structure and imparts a uniform negative charge-to-mass ratio, driving their migration toward the positively charged pole (anode) of the electric field, solely based on size. The percentage of polyacrylamide can be optimized depending on the molecular size range of the sample's components. Small proteins migrate faster through the separating gel than large proteins^{10,11}. In this study, a 6% w/v T polyacrylamide gel was used. Due to the massive size of mucins (MUC5AC/5B), no stacking gel was used to avoid trapping these proteins at the interface. The protocol followed for gel preparation is outlined below:

Gel casting (6% w/v T continuous gel)

- Assemble the glass plates into the casting frame.
- Prepare 20 mL of monomer solution in a 50 mL tube by adding components in the order listed in Table 2. Once TEMED is added (last), the acrylamide begins to polymerize. Immediately mix and transfer the mixture into the casting frame using a micropipette, up to the top.
- Insert the appropriate comb to create sample wells and allow ~ 30 minutes at room temperature for full polymerization.

Table 2: Components for the preparation of 20mL of 6% w/v T polyacrylamide gel.

Components	Volume (mL) of the components needed for casting gels (6% w/v T, volume 20mL)
ddH ₂ O	10.6
30% (w/v) T acrylamide mix	4.0
Tris-HCl (1.5 M, pH 8.8)	5.0
SDS (10% w/v)	0.2
10% (w/v) ammonium persulfate	0.2
TEMED	0.016

As soon as the casting of the gel is done, samples are prepared for loading prior to electrophoresis, based on the protocol described below.

- Add 5x sample buffer (SB) to protein samples at a 1:4 ratio (e.g., 10 µL SB + 40 µL protein sample). The composition of the sample buffer is mentioned in Table 3.
- Mix samples thoroughly by pipetting.
- Heat protein samples for 5 minutes at 95°C.
- Centrifuge all samples before electrophoresis for 5 minutes (10,000 × g, 22°C), to pellet any insoluble debris.

Table 3. Composition of 5x sampling buffer.

Sampling buffer 5x	
Tris-HCl (pH 6.8)	250 mM
SDS	10% w/v
Glycerol	30% v/v
Bromophenol Blue	0.5% w/v
DTT	500 mM

Following the denaturation step, samples are subjected to electrophoretic separation, according to the following analytical workflow:

SDS-PAGE Electrophoresis

- Prepare 1x Running buffer. The composition of the Running buffer is described in Table 4.
- Assemble the electrophoresis apparatus.
- Fill the inner and the outer chamber of the electrophoresis apparatus with 1x running buffer.
- Remove the combs from the gels.
- Wash away thin polyacrylamide threads polymerized within wells, forcefully flushing Running buffer from the chamber into the wells using a Hamilton syringe. This will prevent “wavy” bands that can commonly appear in viscous samples.
- Load protein samples and marker into the wells of the gel.
- Connect the electrophoresis apparatus to the power supply using the color-coded electrical leads and perform electrophoresis (80-120V), until the dye front reaches the bottom of the cassette.
- Turn off the power supply and disconnect the electrical leads.
- Pop open the gel cassettes using a spatula and remove the gels.
- Incubate gels with Blue Silver Coomassie Colloidal Blue Stain according to the following protocol for protein visualization or prepare for immunodetection with Western blot (Western Blot protocol, as described in Section 2.6).

Table 4: Components of 10x Tris-Glycine Running Buffer (pH 8.3, 1 L).

10x Tris-Glycine Running Buffer (pH 8.3, 1L)	
Tris base	30.3 gr
Glycine	144 gr
SDS	10 gr
ddH ₂ O	Add water up to 1 L

For the visualization of the separated proteins, the following “Blue Silver” Colloidal staining protocol was used:

Fixation

- Incubate gels in the fixation solution for 30 minutes under gentle agitation. The composition of the fixation solution is described in Table 5.

Wash

- Wash gels four times with ddH₂O (five minutes each wash) with gentle shaking.

Stain

- Incubate gels in Blue Silver Coomassie Colloidal Blue Stain overnight, at room temperature under gentle agitation. The composition of the Coomassie Stain solution is described in Table 6.

Destain

- Wash the gels repeatedly with ddH₂O until the excess color is completely removed, the background is clear, and the desired color contrast in the protein bands is achieved.
- Take pictures of the gels, using an Imaging System (for this study, ChemiDoc MP Imaging System from Bio-Rad was used).

Table 5: Composition of fixation solution.

Fixation solution	
Methanol	30% v/v
Acetic acid	10% v/v

Table 6: Composition of Blue Silver Coomassie Colloidal Blue Stain

Composition of Blue Silver Coomassie Colloidal Blue Stain	
Coomassie Blue-250	0.12% w/v
Ammonium sulfate	10% w/v
Phosphoric acid	10% v/v
Methanol	20% w/v

2.6 Immunodetection of mucins MUC5AC and MUC5B by Western Blotting

A. Reagents

- Transfer Buffer, 10x (Composition described in Table 7)
- Methanol (Honeywell; 34860)
- Ponceau S solution (Biotium; 22001)
- TBS 10x (Composition described in Table 9)
- Tween 20 (BioRad; 1706531)

- Milk dry powder (Regilait)
- Anti-MUC5B antibody (Mouse) (Abcam; ab105460)
- Anti-MUC5AC antibody (Rabbit), (Abcam; ab198294)
- Anti-mouse IgG, HRP-linked Antibody (Cell Signaling Technology; 7076S)
- Anti-rabbit IgG, HRP-linked Antibody (Cell Signaling Technology; 7074)
- Immobilon ECL Ultra Western HRP Substrate (Solutions A & B; Merck Millipore; WBULS0100)
- ReBlot Plus Strong Antibody Stripping Solution, 10x (Merck Millipore; 2504)
- ddH₂O

B. Equipment & Materials

- Imaging System (ChemiDoc MP; BioRad; 12003154)
- Incubation Shaker (Thermo Fisher; 88881102)
- Power Supply (PowerPac Basic Power Supply; BioRad; 1645050)
- Tetra Cell (Mini-PROTEAN Tetra Cell; BioRad; 1658001)
- Mini Trans-Blot module (BioRad; 1703935)
- Blotting (Whatman) papers (Macherey-Nagel; 218B)
- PVDF Blotting membrane (Macherey-Nagel; 741260)
- Eppendorf tips (10 µL, 200 µL, 1,000 µL)
- Mechanical Micropipettes (100-1,000 µL, 20-200 µL, 0.1-10 µL)
- Falcons (15 mL, 50 mL)
- Eppendorf tubes (2 mL, 1.5 mL)
- Tweezers

C. Procedure

The Western blotting method (protein immunoblotting) is a technique introduced by Towbin et al. in 1979 and is used globally to identify specific proteins in a complex mixture extracted from cell or tissue lysates. Initially, proteins are separated according to their molecular weight by gel electrophoresis and subsequently transferred to a specialized protein-binding membrane. Finally, the protein of interest is detected by a specific antibody. It is therefore understood that antibodies play a central role in the Western blot method, as they guarantee the accuracy, repeatability, and specificity of the technique^{12,13}. The analytical protocol used for this study is described below:

Membrane and gel equilibrium

- Incubate the polyacrylamide gel in 1x Transfer Buffer for 20 minutes, under gentle agitation to remove SDS and salts. The exact composition of the 1x Transfer Buffer, as well as the initial 10x Transfer Buffer used, is described in detail in Tables 7 and 8, respectively.

- Incubate the Whatman papers and sponges in 1x Transfer Buffer for 10 minutes, under gentle agitation.

PVDF activation

- Incubate the PVDF membrane in methanol for 1 minute. This is followed by two washes of the membrane with ddH₂O. The duration of each wash is 2 minutes. After the washes, equilibrate the membrane in 1x Transfer Buffer for 10 minutes.

Table 7: Composition of Transfer Buffer 10x

Transfer Buffer 10x	
Tris Base	30.3 gr
Glycine	144 gr
ddH₂O	Up to 1 L

Table 8: Composition of Transfer Buffer 1x

Transfer Buffer 1x	
Transfer Buffer 10x	100 mL
Methanol	200 mL
ddH₂O	700 mL

(Wet) Electrotransfer

- Assemble the electrotransfer device (blotting sandwich). First, the bottom sponge is placed on the black side of the electrotransfer "cassette," followed by two Whatman papers, the gel, the PVDF membrane, the other two Whatman papers, and the second sponge, respectively. At the end of assembly, the clear side of the "cassette" closes over the black side.
- Place the electrotransfer cassette inside the electrophoresis unit.
- Add an ice pack to the electrophoresis unit and fill the unit with 1x Transfer Buffer.
- Connect the device to the power supply and set the current intensity during electrotransfer to 400 mA for 2 hours.
- After electrotransfer is completed, open the "cassette" and mark the ladder bands on the membrane with a pencil.
- Incubate the membrane in Ponceau S solution, under gentle agitation for 5 minutes, to visualize bands.
- Wash membrane with ddH₂O until membrane is completely destained.

Immunoblotting

- Incubate membrane in 1x TBS solution, under gentle agitation for 15 minutes. The exact composition of the 10x TBS solution (stock), is shown in Table 9.
- Incubate membrane in blocking solution (5% w/v dried milk in TBS-T), under gentle agitation for one hour. The composition of TBS-T is shown in Table 10.

Table 9: Composition of TBS 10x solution

TBS 10x	
1M Tris, pH 7.4	100 mL
5M NaCl	150 mL
ddH₂O	250 mL

Table 10: Composition of TBS-T solution

TBS-T	
TBS 10x	50 mL
ddH₂O	450 mL
Tween 20	500 μ L

- Incubate membrane with the primary antibody of interest overnight. Dilute two primary antibodies of interest, ab105460 (MUC5B) and ab198294 (MUC5AC), at ratios of 1:1,000 and 1:10,000, respectively. The solution used for antibody dilution is the blocking solution (5% w/v dried milk in TBS-T).
- Perform three washes with TBS-T. Incubate the membrane in each wash for 10 minutes.
- Incubate membrane with the corresponding secondary antibody for 1 hour under agitation. The secondary antibody used for the ab105460 (MUC5B) was the anti-mouse IgG antibody, and the secondary antibody used for the ab198294 (MUC5AC) was the anti-rabbit IgG antibody. Dilute both secondary antibodies in TBS-T at a ratio 1:10,000.
- Perform three washes of the membrane with TBS-T. Incubate the membrane in each wash for 10 minutes.

Detection and Reblotting

- Place the PVDF membrane on a plastic film and add the chemiluminescence reagents onto the PVDF membrane using a micropipette. The reagents used in this study are Immulobin ECL Ultra Western HRP Substrate A and Immulobin ECL Ultra Western HRP Substrate B, from Merck. Take 900 μ L from each reagent

and mix them in a new Eppendorf tube. Incubate the membrane with the reagent mixture for 5 minutes.

- Place membrane on the Chemidoc tray and set it to the "Chemiluminescence" mode. Take photos of the membrane using different exposure times on the Chemidoc to determine the optimal exposure time for each antibody.
- Perform three washes of the membrane with TBS-T. Incubate the membrane in each wash for 10 minutes.
- Incubate membrane in 1x Reblotting solution for half an hour, under agitation.
- Perform three washes of the membrane with TBS-T. Incubate the membrane in each wash for 10 minutes.
- Re-block with 5% w/v dried milk/TBS-T, under gentle agitation for one hour before re-probing.

2.7 Filter Aided Sample Preparation (FASP protocol)

A. Reagents

- Urea (Applichem; A1049)
- Iodoacetamide (Merck; 804744)
- Ammonium Bicarbonate (ABC) (Merck; A6141)
- Trypsin (Roche Diagnostics; 11418475001)
- Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) (Applichem; A0697)
- DTT (Applichem; A1101)
- Tris base (Applichem; A1086)
- Hydrochloric acid (HCl) (Merck; 100317)

B. Equipment & Materials

- Refrigerated Microcentrifuge (KUBOTA;3520)
- Speedvac (Thermo Savant; SC110)
- Vibrax (IKA VXR basic; 0002819000)
- Heating Block (Kleinfeld; BT100)
- Thermostat Water Bath (GFL; 1008)
- Centrifugal Filters (NMWCO 30 kDa; Merck; MRCFOR030)
- Mechanical Micropipettes (0.1-10 μ L, 20-200 μ L, 100-1,000 μ L)
- Eppendorf tips (10 μ L, 200 μ L, 1,000 μ L)
- Eppendorf tubes (1.5 mL)
- pH Indicator Paper (PanReac AppliChem; 524164)
- Parafilm wrapping film (Bemis; 1337413)

C. Procedure

Filter-assisted digestion was originally developed by Manza and colleagues in 2005, and the acronym FASP (Filter-Assisted Sample Preparation) was coined by Mann's group in 2009. This protocol is used to prepare samples for mass spectrometry. This technique is based on the use of filters. For this study, Centrifugal Filters (30 kDa; Merck) were used. By using these filters, proteins with a molecular weight greater than 30 kDa are retained on the top of the filter, while salts and some low molecular weight compounds flow through the filter and are discarded¹⁴. The FASP protocol used in the present study is described below:

Reduction and Denaturation

- Transfer 50 μ L from each sample into new Eppendorf tubes.
- Add 3 μ L of DTT to the Eppendorf tubes containing the samples so that the final concentration of DTT is 100 mM.
- Incubate samples at 37°C for 30 minutes in a thermostat water bath.
- Add 200 μ L of urea solution (8 M urea in 0.1 M Tris/HCl, pH 8.5) to the Eppendorf tubes containing the samples.
- Transfer the total volume of the solution (sample + urea) to the filtered Eppendorf tubes.
- Centrifuge the samples for 15 minutes (10,000 \times g, 20°C).

Washing and Alkylation

- Add 200 μ L of freshly prepared urea solution to the filter corresponding to each sample.
- Centrifuge the samples for 15 minutes (10,000 \times g, 20°C).
- Discard the filtrate that has passed through the filters.
- Add 100 μ L of iodoacetamide solution (0.05 M iodoacetamide dissolved in urea) to the filtered Eppendorf tubes.
- Incubate the samples at room temperature for 20 minutes. The samples are placed on the tube shaker (Vibrax IKA VXR basic) and covered with aluminum foil.
- Centrifuge the samples for 10 minutes (10,000 \times g, 20°C).

Buffer exchange

- Add 100 μ L of urea solution to the filtered Eppendorf tubes.
- Centrifuge for 15 minutes (10,000 \times g, 20°C).
- Repeat the previous two steps.
- Add 100 μ L of ABC (0.05 M ABC dissolved in ddH₂O) to the filtered Eppendorf tubes.
- Centrifuge for 10 minutes (10,000 \times g, 20°C).
- Repeat the previous two steps.

Trypsin Digestion

- Prepare Trypsin Solution in ABC buffer (enzyme to protein ratio 1:260 from 1 μ g/ μ l Trypsin Stock Solution).
- Add 50 μ L of the ABC/trypsin solution to the filtered Eppendorf tubes.
- Discard the filtrate and add ddH₂O to the bottom of the filter (to maintain a humid environment). Seal the filter-equipped Eppendorf tubes with parafilm.
- Incubate samples at 37°C for 16–18 hours.

Peptide recovery

- Transfer filters to new Eppendorf tubes labeled accordingly.
- Centrifuge the samples for 20 minutes (10,000 \times g, 20°C).
- Add 50 μ L of ABC.
- Centrifuge the samples for 10 minutes (10,000 \times g, 20°C).
- Repeat the previous two steps twice to maximize recovery.

Acidification and Lyophilization

- Add TFA to samples to acquire a desired pH close to 3. Add more TFA if necessary.
- Place samples in a SpeedVac until they are lyophilized (no liquid residue remains).
- Store samples at 4°C until further processing.

Peptide desalting

- Neutralize the peptide solution and further purify it using an Sp3 peptide cleanup procedure. Add 20 μ L of magnetic bead mixture suspended in 1.2 mL acetonitrile to the peptide mixture (~30 μ L).
- Invert the mixture several times, and after 30 minutes, place the tube on the magnetic stand, and remove the supernatant.
- Wash the beads with the bound peptides twice with 200 μ L 100% v/v acetonitrile.
- Finally, add 50 μ L of water to elute the peptides from the magnetic beads and dry the peptide eluates using a SpeedVac.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the FASP workflow.

2.8 Comparative Label-Free Quantitative Proteomic Analysis by Mass Spectrometry

A. Reagents

- Buffer A (0.1% v/v formic acid in nanopure water)
- Buffer B (0.1% v/v formic acid in 80% v/v acetonitrile in nanopure water)

B. Equipment & Materials

- Q Exactive HF-X Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap, Thermo Scientific
- C18 analytical column, 25 cm (PepSep, beads 1.9 μm , inner diameter 75 μm)
- HPLC vials (200 μL)
- Mechanical Micropipette (1-10 μL)
- Eppendorf tips (10 μL)
- Eppendorf tubes (1.5 mL)

C. Procedure

Proteomic analysis using mass spectrometry was performed on all sputum samples to determine their proteomic profiles. The protocol used is described below:

- Analyze peptide samples on a liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) system consisting of a Dionex Ultimate 3000 nanoRSLC coupled to a Thermo Q Exactive HF-X Orbitrap mass spectrometer.

Chromatography

- Inject the peptide samples directly into a 25-cm C18 analytical column (PepSep, 1.9 μm beads, 75 μm internal diameter) and separate them using a 1h linear gradient. Start with 93% Buffer A and 7% Buffer B. Increase Buffer B to 35% within 40 min, then to 45% within 5 min, and finally to 99% within 0.5 min. Maintain the final concentration for 14.5 min.

MS1 settings (full scan)

- Acquire full MS spectra in profile mode on the Q Exactive HF-X Orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific), operating in the 375–1400 m/z scan range, with 120k resolution, AGC target of 3×10^6 , and a maximum injection time (IT) of 60 ms.

MS2 settings (Data Independent Acquisition (DIA))

- Acquire MS/MS spectra using 8Th isolation windows (39 total cycles), each with 15k resolution, AGC target of 3×10^5 , maximum IT of 22 ms, and normalized collision energy (NCE).
- Analyze each sample in three technical replicates.

2.9 Processing and Visualization of Proteomics Data Based on Mass Spectrometry

A. Procedure

Data processing (DIA-NN)

- Process raw Orbitrap data in DIA-NN 2.2.0 using the Human Reference Proteome (UniProt, 20,659 entries, downloaded 16/10/2025). Perform the search in the no-library mode, allowing up to two missed trypsin cleavages and up to three variable modifications per peptide.
- Generate a spectral library from the DIA runs and reanalyze the data in dual-search mode. Set oxidation of methionine, N-terminal acetylation, and exclusion of N-terminal methionine as variable modifications, and carbamidomethylation of cysteine as a fixed modification. Enable match-between-runs and filter precursor results at 1% FDR. Perform protein inference at the gene level using only proteotypic peptides.

Statistical analysis

- Import the proteomics results into Perseus 1.6.15.0 (MaxQuant environment). Log₂-transform the intensity values and replace missing values from a normal distribution.
- Perform statistical analysis using Student's t-test and calculate FDR based on a randomization-based approach. Generate heat maps using z-scores in Perseus to visualize relative protein abundance across samples.

Visualization and functional analysis

- Generate Venn diagrams from Perseus output using BioVenn.
- Conduct functional enrichment analysis using STRING.

Mucin sequence and glycosylation analysis

- Calculate mucin sequence coverage using an R script. Implement a residue-tracking vector to prevent false positives originating from overlapping peptides; assign “bound” values only to positions uniquely covered by each peptide.
- Visualize the coverage using a Python script that outputs a multiple-alignment-style FASTA representation.
- Annotate the FASTA file with glycosylation sites according to type and position (N-linked, O-linked, C-linked).
- Identify mucin isoforms (MUC1, MUC5AC, MUC5B, MUCL1, MUC2, MUC4, MUC7, MUC13, MUC16) extracted from UniProtKB and manually color-coded regions of homology accordingly.

3. Troubleshooting

A. Solubilization of sputum samples

Challenge: Incomplete lysis or high viscosity.

Solubilization of sputum samples is very challenging due to the biophysical properties (high viscosity, extensive cross-linking) of mucins, which are the main component of airway mucus. These proteins are multimerized via disulfide bridging at their cysteine-rich N- and C-terminal domains. These intermolecular interactions, in combination with the extensive O-glycosylation of mucins, create a viscoelastic network, highly increasing its resistance to solubilization using standard lysis buffers^{5,15}.

Optimization strategies: A. Fresh reducing agents; insufficient solubility after lysis may indicate insufficient reduction of disulfide bonds due to oxidized reducing agents. For this reason, it is crucial that reducing agents, such as dithiothreitol (DTT), are freshly prepared prior to their use. B. Aggressive reduction: If viscosity persists, improved solubilization may be achieved through increased concentration of reducing agents (e.g., DTT up to 100 mM) and/or prolonged incubation time (37°C for 2 hours). C. Mechanical disruption: Combination of chemical reduction with persistent mechanical agitation or vigorous vortexing can enhance the process of solubilization. D. Chaotropic agents: Lysis buffer should contain sufficient denaturants (e.g., 6-8 M Urea and/or 4-6M or Guanidine) to unfold the non-glycosylated domains.

B. Immunodetection of mucins MUC5B & MUC5AC by Western Blot

Challenge 1: Poor migration and smearing

Mucins often exhibit poor electrophoretic migration or appear as high-molecular-weight diffused smears rather than discrete bands due to their exceptionally large size

and extensive glycosylation. Their high molecular weight frequently results in failure to enter the separating polyacrylamide gels ¹⁶.

Optimization strategy: A. Using low-percentage polyacrylamide gels (5-6%) to increase pore size is recommended, to facilitate the migration of these high-molecular-weight proteins. B. To improve gel entry and migration, increasing the concentration of freshly prepared reducing agents included in the sample buffer or prolonging sample heating (60-70°C for 10-15 min), optimizing denaturation, may be beneficial ¹⁷.

Challenge 2: Inefficient transfer

Large mucins are prone to inefficient transfer from the gel onto the membrane during Western blotting ¹⁸.

Optimization strategy: A. Extended wet transfer times are commonly employed to enhance transfer efficiency (> 2 hours at 350-400 mA or overnight at low voltage). B. Adding small amounts of SDS (0.01 - 0.05%) to the transfer buffer can impart residual negative charge and facilitate protein elution from the gel onto the membrane.

Challenge 3: Weak signal

Weak immunodetection signals may result from the inability of antibodies to access the core of the mucins due to steric hindrance by glycans¹⁹.

Optimization strategy A. Optimize blocking conditions (reagents used, incubation time). B. Optimize antibody (Ab) concentrations and incubation times (e.g., primary Ab for 48 hours at 4°C).

C. Proteomic analysis of sputum samples using mass spectrometry analysis

Challenge 1: Low sequence coverage

Proteomic analysis of mucins from sputum samples is challenged by their high molecular weight, reflecting their polymeric structure, and by extensive O-glycosylation, which together generate substantial steric hindrance and limit access of workhorse proteases such as trypsin to the protein backbone^{20,21}. This leads to a lower peptide yield and limited sequence coverage. Another important structural challenge of airway mucins is that their central domains consist of tandem repeated regions, rich in serine, proline, and threonine residues, frequently lacking trypsin cleavage sites (lysine and arginine)².

Optimization strategy: A. Consider using alternative proteases that cleave at different residues, such as GLy-C or Chymotrypsin. B. Perform enzymatic deglycosylation (e.g., O-glycosidase) prior to protein digestion to help expose the protein core and allow peptide recovery.

Challenge 2: Detergent interference

Efficient solubilization of sputum samples required for effective mucin extraction often requires the use of strong detergents, such as SDS. However, incomplete removal of these detergents, particularly SDS, can result in ion suppression and compromised mass spectrometry performance ²².

Optimization strategy: Implementation of buffer-exchange strategies (such as the FASP protocol used in the present study) is essential prior to proteomic analysis. More specifically, FASP allows the depletion of detergents, while high molecular weight proteins are retained. Careful optimization of sample extraction and clean-up steps is required to balance effective solubilization with compatibility for downstream mass spectrometry analysis.

4. References

1. Kirkham, S. *et al.* MUC5B Is the Major Mucin in the Gel Phase of Sputum in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. *Am. J. Respir. Crit. Care Med.* 178, 1033–1039 (2008).
2. Thornton, D. J., Rousseau, K. & McGuckin, M. A. Structure and Function of the Polymeric Mucins in Airways Mucus. *Annu. Rev. Physiol.* 70, 459–486 (2008).
3. Ioannidou, D. *et al.* Proteomic analysis of sputum samples for the isolation and characterization of mucins in patients with bronchial asthma: a pilot study. in *Airway pharmacology and treatment* PA3601 (European Respiratory Society, 2025). doi:10.1183/13993003.congress-2025.PA3601.
4. Ye, Q. *et al.* Mucins and Their Roles in Asthma. *Immunological Reviews* vol. 331 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1111/imr.70034> (2025).
5. Atanasova, K. R. & Reznikov, L. R. Strategies for measuring airway mucus and mucins. *Respir. Res.* 20, 261 (2019).
6. Reddel, H. K. *et al.* Global Initiative for Asthma Strategy 2021: executive summary and rationale for key changes. *European Respiratory Journal* 59, (2022).
7. Efthimiadis, A. *et al.* Methods of sputum processing for cell counts, immunocytochemistry and in situ hybridisation. in *European Respiratory Journal, Supplement* vol. 20 (2002).
8. Grootendorst, D. *et al.* *Induced Sputum in Adolescents with Severe Stable Asthma. Safety and the Relationship of Cell Counts and Eosinophil Cationic Protein to Clinical Severity.*
9. Bradford, M. M. *A Rapid and Sensitive Method for the Quantitation of Microgram Quantities of Protein Utilizing the Principle of Protein-Dye Binding.* *ANALYTICAL BIOCHEMISTRY* vol. 72 (1976).
10. Brunelle, J. L. & Green, R. One-dimensional SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (1D SDS-PAGE). in *Methods in Enzymology* vol. 541 151–159 (Academic Press Inc., 2014).
11. Gallagher, S. R. One-Dimensional SDS Gel Electrophoresis of Proteins. *Curr. Protoc. Protein Sci.* 68, (2012).
12. Meftahi, G. H., Bahari, Z., Zarei Mahmoudabadi, A., Iman, M. & Jangravi, Z. Applications of western blot technique: From bench to bedside. *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education* 49, 509–517 (2021).

13. Taylor, S. C. & Posch, A. The Design of a Quantitative Western Blot Experiment. *Biomed Res. Int.* 2014, 1–8 (2014).
14. Wiśniewski, J. R. Filter-Aided Sample Preparation. in 15–27 (2017). doi:10.1016/bs.mie.2016.09.013.
15. Wagner, C. E., Wheeler, K. M. & Ribbeck, K. Mucins and Their Role in Shaping the Functions of Mucus Barriers. *Annu. Rev. Cell Dev. Biol.* 34, 189–215 (2018).
16. Ramsey, K. A., Rushton, Z. L. & Ehre, C. Mucin Agarose Gel Electrophoresis: Western Blotting for High-molecular-weight Glycoproteins. *Journal of Visualized Experiments* <https://doi.org/10.3791/54153> (2016) doi:10.3791/54153.
17. Kothari, D., Bichala, P. K., Batra, N. & Jain, D. REVIEW: AN APPROACH TO POLYACRYLAMIDE GEL ELECTROPHORESIS (PAGE). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Medicine* 8, 117–133 (2023).
18. Kurien, B. T. & Scofield, R. H. Western Blotting: An Introduction. in 17–30 (2015). doi:10.1007/978-1-4939-2694-7_5.
19. Gilda, J. E. *et al.* Western Blotting Inaccuracies with Unverified Antibodies: Need for a Western Blotting Minimal Reporting Standard (WBMRS). *PLoS One* 10, e0135392 (2015).
20. Ince, D., Lucas, T. M. & Malaker, S. A. Current strategies for characterization of mucin-domain glycoproteins. *Current Opinion in Chemical Biology* vol. 69 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpa.2022.102174> (2022).
21. Guzman, N. A. & Guzman, A. Human Sputum Proteomics: Advancing Non-Invasive Diagnosis of Respiratory Diseases with Enhanced Biomarker Analysis Methods. *International Journal of Translational Medicine* 4, 309–333 (2024).
22. Hengel, S. M. *et al.* Evaluation of SDS depletion using an affinity spin column and IMSMS detection. *Proteomics* 12, 3138–3142 (2012).